

PROVERBS IN THE ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *Nowadays the head of our country pays much attention to education of young generation. A plenty of scientists work with translation of proverbs from one language to another. The sphere of phraseology is wider than other side of linguistic. As it is large sphere there is more problems in phraseology. In lexicology, phonology, lexicography and in other sphere they have their own functions and by this way we can learn their status in linguistic.*

Key words: *Linguistic, communicative, feedback, illustrate, denominations, resultative functions, interjectional phraseological unit.*

Learning foreign languages in our Uzbekistan has become very important events since the first days of the Independence of our country and tourism also developing day by day. Our government which pays much attention to the rising of education levels of people, especially young generation their intellectual growth.

The sphere of phraseology is wider than other side of linguistic. As it is large sphere there is more problems in phraseology. In lexicology, phonology, lexicography and in other sphere they have their own functions and by this way we can learn their status in linguistic. The problem of functions is one of the most urgent issues in phraseology. We maintain, after A.V.Kunin, that communicative, cognitive and nominative functions are constant functions of phraseological units. He gave information that phraseology can guide itself just with functions or styles. Now I want illustrate each types of functions with examples of proverbs and phraseological units. The first one mostly we use it during our speech or with connection to each other. The communicative function of phraseological units consists in their ability to serve as a communicative or message means. Communication presupposes a mutual exchange of statements, and message presupposes the transfer of information without a feedback with the reader or the listener. The communicative phraseological unit function is usually connected with the cultural identity of the utterance. For example: Last year's snow needs not be feared, He

who was once bitten by a snake fears the lizard. As the twenty first century is the modern technology and communication century, that's why mostly we must pay attention to communication features. But by the way we can pass to the nominative function of phraseological units is their relation to objects of the real world, there is a special thing in nominative function. Including situations, and also replacement of these objects in speech activity by their phraseological denominations. The filling of lacunas in the lexical system of the language is characteristic of the nominative function of phraseological units. Mostly in nominative we discuss about exact or real thing. This function is peculiar to the overwhelming majority of phraseological units, as they do not usually have lexical synonyms. The nominative function embraces neutrally-nominal and nominal function. Each function has differences by the way we can pass to the neutrally-nominal *function* is the basic one for phraseological units, e.g. *brown paper*, *red square*. By the checking it we can notice that phrases in communication the fact of a designation of the object is important, and not the stylistic use of the phrase. The nominal function is mostly studied about idiomatic words and expressions also characteristic of semantically transferred phraseological units, but it is not neutral, it is stylistically marked, e.g.: *new broom*, *desperate remedies*, *tales out of school*, *crocodile tears*, *fox's face*. But in the nominative function of phraseological units is their relation to objects of the real world, there is a special thing in nominative function. Mostly in the stories including situations, and also replacement of these objects in speech activity by their phraseological denominations. This function is peculiar to the overwhelming majority of phraseological units, especially as they do not usually have lexical synonyms. As the great linguist said the nominative function embraces neutrally-nominal and nominal function. Before we mentioned cognitive linguistic learns the human beings. The nominative function is closely connected with the nominative one is the cognitive function, i.e. the socially-determined reflection of objects of the real world mediated by consciousness, promoting their cognition. The social determinacy is shown in the fact that, though potential phraseological units are created by separate individuals, these individuals are part of the society, and the realization of the cognitive function by them is possible only on the basis of background knowledge. Cognitive and nominative functions we use in communication, forming a dialectic unity, and all the other functions are realized within the limits of the given functions. The hierarchy of the functional aspect of the phraseological system is seen in it. Among them the semantic functions are voluntaries

because, deictic, resultative functions are found out. After the semantic the volunative function denotes of will expression, sensitivity e.g.: *wish smb well* with the meaning of 'to wish good luck, success to smb, to treat smb benevolently': *I wish Jane Fairfax very well; but she tires me to death*. In the deictic function mostly we can mention spatial or time localization of the action, phenomenon, event which is relative to the reference point, relevant within the limits of one or another speech situation, i.e. we can give example personal deixis exists: a person, a place or time can be the reference point. According to this fact three types of deixis are singled out: personal, spatial and time ones, e.g.: *Time and tide wait for no man; It is too late to lock the stable door when the horse is stolen;*

As a rule proverbs also have semantic, syntactic, grammatical categories. The semantic sphere of proverbs is very wide and we cannot limit them. The proverbs describe the every branch of people's life: the economical, psychological, cultural and etc. The fact is that proverbs and sayings are similar in meaning in spite of their diversity in form and language. To prove they said above some examples:

A bird in hand is worth two in the bush.

Un tiens vaut mieux que deux tu'auras.

Un chien vivant vaut mieux qu'un lion mort.

Лучше синица в руках, чем журавль на небе.

Nasiya saryog'dan, naqd o 'pka yaxshi.

The stylistic function realizes connotative features of a phraseological unit in speech. In the language there is only stylistic colouring. The idea about it is given by marks and comments in stylistic dictionaries which, unfortunately, are still far from being perfect. Comparison of a phraseological unit with its variable prototypical combination of words also helps to reveal stylistic colouring. Developing, the phraseological theory in its functional-semantic aspect, S.G. Gavrin singles out some functions of phraseological units. These functions are also characteristic of English phraseological units: a) the expressively-figurative function (*pulls one's leg; put the cart before the horse*); b) the emotionally-expressive function (*damn your eyes! My foot!*); c) the function of speech concision by omitting some components (*Don't teach your grandmother!* instead of *don't teach your grandmother to suck eggs!*). Proverbs, especially short ones, even not of the reduced kind we mostly use it during the speech, carry out **the function of speech lionizations**, e.g.: *Give a dog a bad name and hang him* meaning once someone has acquired a bad reputation, it is almost impossible for him to shake it off, and even his most innocent actions will be misunderstood'.

Evidently, that the definition is almost four times as long as the proverb itself. In it we can include the semantic compression, characteristic of phraseological units, is one of the instances of language economy. The last function we can say the compensatory function which is realized in the description of strong sincere emotional experience, affect, when one's speech is complicated and an interjectional phraseological unit is the only content of the whole remark.

All in all, with the proverbs we can show the social, cultural life of one nation.

REFERENCE:

1. Gläser Rosamarie. The Stylistic Potential of Phraseological Units in the Light of Genre Analysis. In: Cowie Anthony Paul (ed.): Phraseology. Theory, Analysis and Applications. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1998. - P. 125-143
2. Grant Lynn. Frequency of 'core idiom' in the British National Corpus (BNC). // International Journal of Corpus Linguistics, 2005. - № 10/4. - P. 429-451